

D2.3 SWOT ANALYSIS OF EXISTING TOOLS/PLATFORMS FOR SHARING FOOD DATA

WP2, T2.1

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TECHNICAL REFERENCES

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- *PU = Public
- SEN= sensitive

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1 INTRODUCTION

The SPOON project aims to transform the European food system by placing citizens and their local realities at the research and innovation centre. In response to the growing complexity of challenges such as food waste, food insecurity, unhealthy diets, and lack of transparency, SPOON promotes a paradigm shift from top-down approaches to citizen-driven, data-informed, and cross-sectoral transformation.

At the core of the projects are Citizen Science Labs (CSLs)¹ and Behaviour Change Intervention (BCIs), where citizens will actively contribute to collecting, analysing, and interpreting food-related data. SPOON seeks to foster inclusive knowledge generation, behavioural change, and more effective, evidence-based food policy development through these activities.

SPOON is developing a modular digital toolset that supports secure and participatory data flows to enable these processes. This toolset consists of:

- DataU: a GDPR-compliant consent management platform,
- Data Wallet: a personal, encrypted data storage solution,
- Questionnaire Tool: a customisable survey platform,
- SPOON Data Hub: a repository for anonymised data collected within CSLs,
- And a connection to existing data-sharing platforms (e.g., DJustConnect and DIH Agrifood Data Space), all designed to ensure transparency, interoperability, and sovereignty of citizen data.

Figure 1: Overview of the SPOON Digital Toolset and its core components (Source: SPOON Grant Agreement)

¹ A Citizen Science Lab (CSL) is a collaborative space, physical, digital, or hybrid, where citizens actively contribute to scientific research by collecting, sharing, or analysing data, often in partnership with researchers and organizations.

This report contributes to the toolset’s development by fulfilling the objective of identifying and analysing external digital tools and platforms that collect data related to food production and consumption, particularly those involving direct citizen engagements. These include tools already used by SPOON partners, especially those tested or piloted within CSL settings, and broader digital solutions for citizen engagement. The report delivers a structured inventory of these digital solutions accompanied by a comparative SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats, Guerel, E., & Tat, M., 2017), considering their technical functionalities, usability, potential for citizen involvement, data quality, scalability, and interoperability with other platforms.

The report presents a structured inventory of 17 digital tools and a comparative SWOT analysis. The analysis goes beyond technical functionalities and evaluates the tools based on their usability, potential for citizen involvement, quality and type of data collected, customizability for different audiences or purposes, scalability for larger user bases or datasets, and interoperability with other platforms and systems.

Special attention is given to tools enabling citizens to contribute data on food production and consumption while supporting co-creation, feedback loops, and participatory engagement mechanisms. The focus is, therefore, not only on what tools can do but also on how well they can align with participatory and ethical values embedded in SPOON’s vision.

The outcome of this deliverable will inform further project activities, particularly those related to the selection, adaptation, or integration of digital tools within the SPOON pilot countries. This will include their use in CSLs and BCIs, with the ultimate goal of enabling active citizen participation and supporting data-driven transformation towards healthier, more inclusive, and sustainable food systems.

2 METHODOLOGY OVERVIEW

This chapter outlines the methodological approach to identify, select, and analyse digital tools and platforms for collecting citizen-generated food production and consumption data in sustainable food systems. The process was designed to ensure the assessment is evidence-based and closely aligned with practical realities.

2.1 TOOL IDENTIFICATION PROCESS

Identifying relevant digital tools began with a comprehensive mapping process that combined desk research (drawing on literature, digital innovation portals, open-source repositories, and curated databases of technology tools) with direct inputs from project partners, including CSLs. Partners were invited to share tools they currently use, have experience with, plan to adopt, or consider potentially useful for citizen science, food system engagement, and data

collection related to food production and consumption—the initial mapping matrix used for collecting and describing these tools is available in Appendix 1.

This mapping effort yielded various tools and platforms, including mobile applications, web-based platforms, collaborative dashboards, and participatory data collection systems. Particular attention was placed on tools that facilitate citizen involvement in data generation, self-reporting, or co-creation activities, especially those capable of gathering, visualising, and interpreting citizen-generated data on food practices, consumption patterns, and food waste. Inputs from social science experts and technical developers were used to assess each tool's usability, adaptability, and potential fit within the CSL digital environment.

However, not all the initially gathered tools met the selection criteria for further analysis. A clear relevance and quality criteria were applied to ensure methodological coherence and alignment with project objectives. These criteria included:

- Actual or intended use by CSLs, indicating direct relevance and potential for piloting.
- Alignment with project goals, particularly regarding citizen engagement and support for food-related data flows.
- Technical maturity, covering aspects such as stability, user-friendliness, and ease of deployment.
- Functional capacity, especially regarding interoperability, data-sharing potential, and support for participatory or co-creation activities.

Tools that did not sufficiently match these criteria due to limited documentation, lack of technical maturity, or poor fit with the project goals were not selected for in-depth analysis in the next phase. Their exclusion does not imply a lack of quality or value but reflects their lower relevance to the specific operation and strategic needs of citizen science data gathering.

2.2 SWOT FRAMEWORK DESIGN

Each selected tool was assessed using a structured SWOT analysis framework to ensure consistency and comparability across the evaluation. The framework was designed to evaluate each tool's internal and external dimensions relevant to the tool's performance and potential contribution to citizen science and food system engagement.

Table 1: Classification of internal and external factors in relation to SWOT components for digital tools assessment

SWOT	Factor type	Description
Strengths (S)	Internal	Positive technical and functional characteristics of tools (e.g. usability, modularity, scalability, openness)
Weakness (W)	Internal	Limitations in tool design or performance (e.g. poor user interface (UI), lack of interoperability, rigid architecture)

Opportunities (O)	External	Enabling trends and conditions (e.g. alignment with policy priorities, potential for scaling, civic engagement)
Threats (T)	External	External risks (e.g. GDPR non-compliance, digital exclusion, vendor lock-in, lack of long-term support or trust)

As seen in the above table, internal factors refer to technical and functional characteristics inherent to the tools, which may act as strengths or weaknesses depending on their implementation quality and relevance in participatory settings. External factors relate to the broader environment in which the tools operate. They are assessed as opportunities or threats based on alignment with emerging trends, regulatory conditions, and potential adoption barriers. This classification provides a structured basis for the SWOT analysis presented in this deliverable.

Each tool was evaluated using the same guiding questions and criteria, enabling a balanced, replicable, and transparent evaluation process. Preliminary assessments were reviewed internally and validated through expert (IT and social science) feedback to minimise subjective bias. As presented in the following chapters, this process ensured a solid foundation for synthesising meaningful insights across the different tools.

2.3 DATA SOURCES AND LIMITATIONS

The content analyses presented in this deliverable were informed by publicly available information, internal project knowledge, and input gathered through partner consultations. For most tools, data were collected from various sources, including official websites, user documentation, online feature descriptions, open-access demo versions, academic publications, and third-party evaluations where available. These sources helped assess the tools' functional and technical characteristics and broader relevance to citizen science and participatory governance in the context of food systems.

In addition, the project partners, particularly those with hands-on experience using the tools in real-world settings, provided insights. Their feedback enriched the evaluation by contextualising technical descriptions with practical reflections on usability, flexibility, and integration potential.

However, several limitations were encountered during the assessment process. In many cases, publicly available information was limited, outdated, or promotional, lacking the technical depth or critical analysis needed for a comprehensive evaluation. Some tools had restricted access, required a paid license, or did not offer free demo versions, which limited the ability to conduct direct testing. Furthermore, certain tools lacked active user communities or transparent development roadmaps, making it challenging to evaluate long-term

sustainability, ongoing support, and potential for future development. These challenges were partially mitigated through expert judgment and validation by project partners familiar with the tools. Nonetheless, they highlight important considerations that may need to be addressed if a specific tool is to be implemented, including the need for additional user testing, piloting, or stakeholder feedback in the upcoming implementation phase.

Despite these challenges, combining sources provided a sufficiently robust foundation for the initial SWOT screening. The findings presented here should be considered indicative and formative to support strategic decisions in selecting, designing, and deploying future SPOON digital tools.

3 OVERVIEW OF EXISTING TOOLS

This chapter presents a structured overview of external digital tools relevant to participatory processes, citizen engagement, and community-based data collection, particularly in the domains of food systems, sustainability, and community-driven contexts. The tools included in this overview vary in scope, functionality, and user orientation, ranging from simple data collection mechanisms such as surveys and crowdsourced reporting to more complex platforms for collaborative decision-making, food-sharing coordination, or participatory budgeting. Some focus on democratic participation, others on food redistribution, neighbourhood-level interaction, or behavioural data sharing.

Each tool is briefly profiled, with attention to its main purpose, core features, application domain, technical maturity level, target user groups, and, where available, its current level of adoption or implementation. The tools were selected based on their potential applicability within SPOON's CSLs, alignment with citizen science principles, and capacity to support more inclusive, transparent, and sustainable food systems.

Who's the Boss

URL: <https://www.imarkatoukatanaloti.gr>

Who's the Boss is a consumer-driven initiative that empowers consumers to define product specifications, such as quality, origin, and price, and supports fair producer remuneration. It enables citizens to influence market decisions by supporting ethical and sustainable producers. It empowers users to express preferences through voting campaigns tied to product choices in supermarkets. This participatory model has led to the development over 30 products, including milk, butter, eggs, vegetables and fruits. It is technically mature and publicly maintained, geared toward conscious consumers and advocacy networks seeking systemic change in the food system. The initiative has been successfully replicated under different names in several countries (Germany, Belgium, Greece, Spain, Italy, Morocco, Netherlands, United Kingdom, and United States).

Bring the Food

URL: <https://bringfood.org/en/>

BringTheFood is a web-based application developed by the ICT4G (ICT for Good) research unit at Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) in Trento, Italy. Launched in 2012, the platform facilitates the donation and recovery of surplus food by connecting donors with charitable organisations in need, such as supermarkets, restaurants, caterers, and private individuals. Donors can list available food items, specifying details like quantity and expiration dates, while recipient organisations can view these listings and arrange for prompt collection, often within 24 hours. The system also generates necessary documentation for tax benefits, aligning with Italian legislation that encourages food donations. As of 2023, BringTheFood has enabled the recovery and distribution of over 10 million meals, averaging more than 100,000 kilograms of food per month. The platform has been adopted by various organisations, including the Banco Alimentare della Calabria and ACLI Padova's Rete Solida project, and continues to expand its reach through initiatives like the "Certified Donor" program and educational projects aimed at reducing food waste.

Open Food Network

URL: <https://www.openfoodnetwork.org>

Open Food Network (OFN) is a global, open-source platform cooperative launched in 2012 to support ethical, transparent, and community-driven food systems. Designed specifically for food enterprises, OFN enables farmers, producers, food hubs, and cooperatives to create and manage online shops, facilitating direct sales to consumers and collaboration among producers. The platform accommodates complex food-specific needs, such as variable weights and subscription models, and supports multiple order cycles, delivery options, and payment integrations. As of 2023, OFN operates in over 20 countries, connecting more than 7,000 producers with local communities. Its decentralised governance model empowers local instances to adapt the software to regional contexts while contributing to a shared global codebase. Beyond software, OFN offers resources, training, and a supportive community to help build resilient local food economies.

CamBuildr

URL: <https://cambuildr.com>

CamBuildr is a digital campaign platform developed by Campaigning Software GmbH, which is based in Vienna, Austria. Launched in 2021, the platform is designed to support the creation and execution of multi-channel advocacy campaigns, particularly for NGOs, political organisations, and grassroots movements. It offers an intuitive drag-and-drop editor, GDPR-compliant data handling, analytics dashboards, A/B testing features, and centralised supporter management tools. CamBuildr has been used by more than 100 European clients, including the Austrian Red Cross and political campaigns. The platform has supported over 5,000 campaigns and reached over 25 million people. While it is not specific to the food sector, its communication and mobilisation capabilities make it a relevant digital asset for awareness-driven campaigns and visually compelling storytelling.

Decidim

URL: <https://decidim.org>

Decidim is a free, open-source platform developed by the City of Barcelona in 2016 to support participatory democracy. Designed for structured citizen involvement, it offers proposals, debates, participatory budgeting, surveys, and voting modules. Built on Ruby on Rails with a modular, multilingual interface, it ensures GDPR compliance and high configurability. Since its launch, Decidim has been adopted by over 400 institutions in more than 30 countries, including cities like Helsinki and Lyon. In its first use in Barcelona, around 40,000 citizens submitted over 10,000 proposals for the city's strategic plan. The platform is maintained by the Metadecidim community, which includes developers, public officials, and civil society actors committed to democratic digital governance.

Consul

URL: <https://consuldemocracy.org/features/>

Consul is a free, open-source digital platform developed by the Madrid City Council in 2015 to enhance citizen participation in governmental decision-making. It offers a comprehensive suite of tools, including participatory budgeting, citizen proposals, collaborative legislation, debates, and voting mechanisms. The highly customisable platform allows institutions to adapt it to their specific needs. Since its inception, Consul has been adopted by over 250 cities and organisations worldwide, including major capitals like Paris, Madrid, and Buenos Aires. More than 200 million EUR has been allocated through participatory budgeting processes facilitated by the Consul. The platform is maintained by the Consul Democracy Foundation, which was established in 2019 to support its global user community and ongoing development. Consul's widespread adoption and adaptability make it a leading tool for fostering transparent and inclusive democratic processes.

Polis

URL: <https://pol.is/home>

Polis is an open-source, web-based platform developed by the Computational Democracy Project to facilitate large-scale, real-time conversation among diverse groups. Participants can submit short statements and vote on others' submissions, with responses categorised as "agree", "disagree", or "pass". Polis employs statistical analysis and machine learning to identify opinion clusters and highlight areas of consensus and divergence within a group. This approach encourages constructive dialogue by surfacing statements that bridge dividers rather than amplifying polarising views. A lightweight, cloud-based tool for gathering large-scale opinions, using machine learning to cluster participants based on shared viewpoints. It is especially useful in reviling consensus and outliers within group dialogue. The platform is technically solid and often used by governments and research groups.

Synthetron

URL: <https://www.synthetron.com/en>

Synthetron is a web-based platform developed by the Belgian company Synthetron N.V. to facilitate large-scale, real-time, anonymous text-based discussion. Designed for organisations seeking deep insights into stakeholder opinions, it enables up to 1,000 participants per session to share and evaluate ideas collaboratively. The platform's unique evolutionary crowdsourcing algorithm ensures that the most supported ideas gain prominence, fostering consensus-driven dialogues. Sessions typically last about an hour and are moderated to maintain focus and productivity. Synthetron has been utilised by various entities, including the City of Amsterdam, Rabobank, and the European Investment Bank, to engage employees, customers, and citizens in meaningful conversations. Its application spans change management and policy development to customer research and community engagements. Synthetron provides organisations with actionable insights to inform decision-making processes by combining qualitative depth with quantitative scalability.

EngagementHQ

URL: <https://go.engagementhq.com/>

EngagementHQ is a cloud-based community engagement platform developed by Bang the Table (now part of Granicus), designed to facilitate inclusive and transparent public participation. It offers a suite of nine interactive tools, including Surveys, Polls, Forums, Ideas, Guestbook, Q&A, Stories, Places, and Budgeting, to support various engagement strategies. The platform features a Participant Relationship management system for stakeholder segmentation, customisable branding, and integration with services like Mailchimp and OpenCities. EngagementHQ is ISO 27001 certified with GDPR compliant, ensuring robust data security and privacy. Adopted by over 1,000 organisations worldwide, including governments in Australia, the UK, and the US, it has been instrumental in projects like participatory budgeting and urban planning consultations. Advanced analytics, sentiment analysis, and real-time reporting tools enable administrators to derive actionable insights from community feedback, enhancing decision-making processes.

Go Vocal

URL: <https://www.govocal.com/>

Go Vocal is a digital community engagement platform developed by the Brussels-based company Go Vocal (formerly CitizenLab) in 2015. Designed to facilitate inclusive and participatory decision-making, the platform offers tools, including surveys, ideation sessions, participatory budgeting, mapping, and proposal submissions. Its AI-powered analytics feature, sensemaking, helps administrators efficiently process and interpret community feedback. Go Vocal supports multilingual interfaces and complies with GDPR and ISO/IEC 27001:2013 standards, ensuring data security and privacy. Over 500 governments and organisations have adopted the platform worldwide, including cities like Seattle, Lancaster, and St. Louis, where it has been instrumental in engaging thousands of residents in policy development and resource allocation. Go Vocal's open-source model allows for customisation and scalability, making it a versatile tool for various community engagement initiatives.

MindMixer

URL: <https://www.mindmixer.com/>

MindMixer is a web-based community engagement platform launched in 2011 by urban planners Nick Bowden and Nathan Preheim in Omaha, Nebraska. Designed as a virtual town hall, it enables municipalities, school districts, and organisations to gather public input through tools like surveys, polls, idea submissions, and interactive mapping. MindMixer has facilitated over 170,000 conversations and engaged more than 225,000 contributors across 1,300 communities, including cities like Los Angeles, Phoenix, and Kansas City, as well as institutions like the National Park Service and various school districts. The platform supports features such as gamification to incentivise participation, integration with social media for broader outreach, and Esri-based mapping to tie feedback to specific locations. Its user-friendly interface and focus on transparency make it a valuable tool for organisations seeking to involve community members in decision-making processes.

MetroQuest

URL: <https://www.metroquest.com/>

MetroQuest is a web-based public engagement platform developed by MetroQuest Inc., a Canadian company established in the late 1990s. Tailored for urban and transportation planning, it enables agencies to create interactive, visually engaging surveys that educate participants and collect informed input. The platform supports various modules, including priority ranking, trade-off analysis, mapping, and scenario exploration, facilitating comprehensive community feedback. Notably, MetroQuest has been utilised by numerous transportation departments and planning organisations across North America, such as the Colorado Department of Transportation and the City of Peterborough, to engage thousands of residents in planning initiatives. In July 2023, MetroQuest was acquired by Social Pinpoint, aiming to integrate and enhance digital public engagement solutions.

Nextdoor

URL: <https://nextdoor.com/>

Nextdoor is a hyperlocal social networking platform founded in 2008 and launched in the US in 2011. It is designed to connect neighbours within specific geographic areas, facilitating communication and collaboration on local matters. Users must verify their addresses to join their neighbourhood's network, ensuring that interactions are among actual residents. The platform enables members to share information about community events, safety concerns, local services, and items for sale or free. As of 2023, Nextdoor operates in 11 countries, including the US, UK, Canada, and several European nations, encompassing over 340,000 neighbourhoods globally. With more than 100 million verified users, it is a vital tool for fostering community engagement and resilience.

Hoplr

URL: <https://www.hoplr.com/>

Hoplr is a private, ad-free social network launched in Belgium in 2014 by Jennick Scheerlinck and Jonas Heirwegh. Its mission is to strengthen local communities by facilitating neighbour-to-neighbour interaction, mutual support, and civic participation. Accessible via web and mobile apps, Hoplr connects residents based on verified addresses within geographically defined neighbourhoods, ensuring privacy and trust. Users can exchange goods and services, organise local events, offer or request assistance, and participate in community discussions. The platform also provides a dedicated dashboard for local governments and public services to share announcements and gather feedback without accessing private conversations. As of 2023, Hoplr is active in over 2,500 neighbourhoods across Belgium, the Netherlands, and Luxembourg, with more than 800,000 households registered. Notably, in the municipality of Terneuzen, 32% of households actively use Hoplr weekly, and over 40% of users meet a new neighbour in person within their first year on the platform.

Commonplace

URL: <https://www.commonplace.is>

Commonplace is a UK-based digital citizen engagement platform facilitating inclusive and transparent community participation in urban planning and development projects. Launched in 2014, it enables local authorities, developers, and organisations to gather public input through interactive tools such as surveys, idea boards, and map-based feedback mechanisms. The platform's features include real-time data analysis, AI-powered insights, and customisable engagement sites, allowing users to visualise community sentiments and priorities effectively. Commonplace has been utilised in over 3,500 projects across the UK, engaging millions of residents in shaping their local environments. Notable implementations include collaborations with the Mayor of London, Leeds City Council, and Westminster City Council. In 2025, Commonplace was acquired by Zencity, a global community engagement company, enhancing its capabilities with advanced analytics and expanding its reach to a broader audience.

EpiCollect5

URL: <https://five.epicollect.net/>

Epicollect5 is a free, open-source mobile and web-based data collection platform developed by the Centre for Genomic Pathogen Surveillance at the University of Oxford. It enables users to create customisable forms and collect data, including GPS coordinates, photos, videos, and barcodes, via Android and iOS devices, even in offline environments. The platform supports public and private projects, offering granular user access controls and role assignments. Collected data is synchronised to a central server, which can be viewed in tables, maps, and charts and exported in CSV or JSON formats. As of 2025, Epicollect5 hosts over 160,000 projects, with over 408,000 users contributing to over 61 million entries. The platform is widely used in citizen science, environmental monitoring, public health, and academic research. Epicollect5 also offers an API for integration with external systems and supports data visualisation through tools like Google Maps and Microreact.

Kialo

URL: <https://www.kialo.com>

Kialo is an online structured debate platform launched in 2017 by Kialo Inc., headquartered in Brooklyn and Berlin. It allows users to engage in rational, civil discussions by mapping arguments in a tree-like structure, distinguishing between supporting (Pro) and opposing (Con) points beneath a central thesis. As of July 2023, Kialo hosts over 18,000 public debates with over 720,000 claims and 1 million votes across various topics, including philosophy, policy, ethics, and science. The platform's design emphasises clarity and depth, enabling users to visualise complex discussions and understand different perspectives. Features like "Impact" ratings help highlight the most influential arguments, while the "Perspectives" tool allows users to view debates from various viewpoints. Kialo also supports private debates, making it suitable for organisations and educational institutions seeking structured deliberation tools.

Kialo Edu, a variant tailored for educational settings, offers additional functionalities such as grading tools, anonymous participation, and integrations with platforms like Google Classroom and Moodle. Educators worldwide utilise Kialo Edu to enhance critical thinking and structured argumentation skills among students.

4 INDIVIDUAL SWOT ANALYSIS OF EXISTING TOOLS

This chapter presents the individual SWOT analysis of each digital tool identified in the previous section. This analysis aims to provide a structured understanding of each tool's potential and limitations concerning the SPOON project's goals. The assessments consider internal factors such as functionality, user experience, flexibility, and external factors, including scalability, relevance to citizen science, legal compliance, and integration potential. Each SWOT matrix is accompanied by a short interpretation highlighting key implications for possible use in developing Living Labs or the SPOON tool.

WHO'S THE BOSS	
<p>Purpose: Consumer awareness, voting on sustainability practices</p> <p>Domain: Citizen-driven market transparency</p> <p>Technical maturity: Operational and publicly accessible (Greece and other countries)</p>	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A clear focus on citizen empowerment in food systems. - Easy-to-use interface. - Successfully links consumer choices to supply chain accountability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited language availability and localisation features. - Country- and context-specific implementation. - It is not designed for multi-step deliberative processes.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential to replicate/adapt in other EU countries to enhance citizen-market linkages. - It can serve as a model for consumer-led sustainability standards in food systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low uptake outside the original policy and retail context. - Uncertain long-term funding and business model. - The platform's simplicity may limit scalability.
<p>Who's the Boss is a promising example of market-facing civic tech that links consumers' opinions to sustainability impact. Although not designed for deep co-creation, it can serve as a high-visibility entry point in awareness-raising campaigns. SPOON's value lies in mobilising consumer involvement and engaging the public through structured, outcome-oriented participation.</p>	

CAMBUILDR
<p>Purpose: Visual mockup and campaign builder</p> <p>Domain: Digital content creation, marketing</p>

Technical maturity: Commercial, stable product	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visually appealing and fast content generation. - Ideal for creating branded or educational campaign materials. - User-friendly and low technical barrier. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lacks participatory decision-making features. - There is no support for deliberation, collaboration, or voting. - Minimal alignment with food system or civic engagement context.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can support storytelling or awareness-building campaigns, outreach, or youth-oriented communication in CSLs. - Possible integration into broader campaigns with participatory layers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is a high risk of being perceived as superficial or disconnected from engagement logic. - More participatory or domain-specific tools may replace it.
<p>While not a participatory tool per se, CamBuildr can complement engagement activities by supporting visually engaging materials or narrative elements. It could be particularly useful for awareness campaigns within SPOON or showcasing results.</p>	

DECIDIM	
Purpose: Structured participatory democracy	
Domain: Civic tech, municipal decision-making	
Technical maturity: Highly mature, open-source platform, widely deployed	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Robust and modular participatory architecture. - Supports full participatory cycles, including proposals, debates, surveys, voting, and co-creation. - Transparent and community-driven development model. - Extensive documentation and multilingual support. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires significant configuration and technical support. - It may be complex for small-scale or short-term activities without IT support. - Backend management requires technical capacity. - A clear facilitation strategy is needed to maintain engagement.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highly adaptable for participatory governance in food systems. - Support complex engagement processes across stakeholder groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk of low engagement without active facilitation. - Complexity may discourage use for basic applications. - Requires ongoing maintenance and capacity building.

Decidim is one of the most capable tools for structured participation and policy co-creation. For SPOON it offers long-term value in establishing transparent, participatory governance processes. However, it must be supported by appropriate human and technical resources.

CONSUL	
Purpose: Participatory budgeting, collaborative governance	
Domain: Civic engagement, public governance	
Technical maturity: A Mature, open-source platform used globally by local governments	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open-source with strong institutional credibility. - Build-in modules for participatory budgeting, proposals, debates, and voting. - Multilingual support. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Less intuitive interface compared to newer platforms. - Relatively static design and limited real-time features. - Backend management may be challenging for non-experts. - Required trained moderators.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It can be applied to food policy co-creation, budget allocation for food-related community actions, or LL governance. - A good foundation for CS integration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It may require custom development to integrate with digital architecture. - Engagement fatigue or confusion if not adequately supported.
<p>Consul provides a stable and trusted environment for structured public participation, particularly around budgeting and decision-making. Its open-source nature and international use cases make it a solid candidate for SPOON, especially where financial decisions or co-created policies are in focus. However, careful onboarding and adaptation would be necessary to ensure usability and citizen uptake in food system contexts.</p>	

POLIS	
Purpose: Large-scale opinion mapping and structured deliberation	
Domain: Public consultation, deliberation	
Technical maturity: Cloud-based, research-validated	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enables real-time visualisation of group consensus and divergence. - Supports open and inclusive participation without forcing consensus. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited functionality beyond opinion mapping. - It does not support deliberative features like proposals or voting.

- Used in multiple civic and governmental contexts.	- Requires expert moderation to interpret the cluster accurately.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
- Useful for gauging citizen attitudes on food behaviours, dietary shifts, or policy options. - Can complement co-creation tools by identifying areas of convergence or tension.	- Misinterpretation of visual outputs without expert moderation. - Accessibility limitations for non-digital or low-literacy users.
Polis excels at mapping public opinion in an accessible, visual way, making it ideal for early-stage consultations or topic exploration. It is best used with other tools supporting deeper engagement or follow-up actions.	

SYNTHETRON	
Purpose: Facilitate group dialogues	
Domain: Strategic reflection, stakeholder consultation	
Technical maturity: Mature commercial platform, professionally maintained	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
- Supports high-quality qualitative insight. - Allows structured, anonymous, real-time discussion. - Outputs are synthesised automatically. - Useful for simulating focus groups at scale.	- Requires trained facilitators for effective use. - Not open source; commercial license required. - Limited usability for grassroots or informal engagement.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
- Suitable for expert consultations on food system innovation. - Can support co-design workshops and stakeholder dialogues in CSLs.	- High cost and licensing may deter uptake in open, community-driven contexts. - Dependence on facilitation limits scalability for large citizen groups.
Synthetron is a powerful tool for structured and high-level dialogue, especially useful when gathering strategic insights from stakeholders. However, due to its closed nature and facilitation demands, its use may be limited to targeted events or expert panels.	

ENGAGEMENTHQ	
Purpose: Public engagement via surveys, forums, and events	
Domain: Local government, community input	
Technical maturity: Highly developed commercial platform with extensive deployment	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feature-rich: mapping, surveys, idea boards, forums, event modules. - Professional UI/UX and support services. - Built-in analytics and user management tool. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A commercial license is required at a high licensing cost. - Potential vendor lock-in. - Customisation and integration options may be limited.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Suitable for well-funded LL with strong institutional support. - Can structure multi-modal participation in one place. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It may be too expensive for small organisations. - Feature overload can reduce usability for basic needs.
<p>EngagementHQ is a full-featured engagement suite that could serve SPOON's structured, visual, and multi-modal engagement needs. However, its proprietary nature may limit long-term flexibility.</p>	

GO VOCAL	
<p>Purpose: Local government engagement and feedback Domain: Civic communication and reporting Technical maturity: Commercially hosted, user-friendly</p>	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simple tools for surveys, polls, and quick feedback. - Integrated analytics for local administrators. - Mobile-friendly and accessible. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited functionality beyond feedback collection. - Closed system with few integration options. - There is no support for co-creation or sustained dialogue.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good fit for light-touch engagement or municipal service evaluation. - It could be paired with co-design tools for broader workflows. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visibility and usage may be confined to formal contexts. - Low depth of engagement limits its usefulness for systemic transformation.
<p>Go Vocal offers a low-barrier tool for capturing quick input from the public but lacks the capacity for deep or iterative engagement. However, it may complement other tools, especially in early consultation phases.</p>	

MINDMIXER	
<p>Purpose: Community feedback and idea generation Domain: Public participation</p>	

Technical maturity: Legacy platform; current status unclear	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Focused on community idea sharing and prioritisation. - The interface was originally user-friendly. - Pioneering platform for digital civic dialogue. - Previously offered intuitive idea-sharing and prioritisation features. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The platform may be outdated and unsupported. - Lack of transparency around data handling or technical roadmap.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides design inspiration for modern participatory platforms. - The historical model of digital civic dialogue is still relevant. - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High risk of obsolescence. - It may lack GDPR compliance and technical compatibility.
MindMixer offers useful historical insights into civic tech design but may no longer be viable for direct integration into SPOON due to limited recent activity and support.	

METROQUEST	
Purpose: Public input for planning and design	
Domain: Transportation and urban planning	
Technical maturity: Commercial platform with a strong reputation in the planning sectors	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visually engaging surveys and scenario-based consultations. - Strong track record in urban and infrastructure planning. - Useful for spatially anchored public input. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Designed for specific urban planning contexts. - High cost and licensing requirements. - Not easily adaptable to broader engagement needs.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It could be adapted to visualise preferences for food infrastructure, markets, or urban agriculture zones. - Potential use in spatial planning. - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited flexibility outside its original urban planning context. - Cost may outweigh benefits for food-related use cases.
MetroQuest offers an advanced visual feedback platform for spatial planning. Its utility may be restricted to specialised cases involving food infrastructure planning in urban settings. Its cost and domain specificity limit wider applicability.	

NEXTDOOR	
<p>Purpose: Neighbourhood communication and mobilisation</p> <p>Domain: Community networking</p> <p>Technical maturity: Very high, globally deployed, commercial social network</p>	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Large and active user base. - Easy onboarding and intuitive use. - Effective for hyperlocal information sharing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is not designed for structured participation or feedback processes. - Data governance concerns, closed platform. - Algorithms may reduce transparency or inclusiveness.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Effective for outreach, awareness campaigns, and mobilising participation in food events or surveys. - It can support informal engagement and trust-building. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited control over platform functionality and data. - Unsuitable for in-depth dialogue or co-creation processes.
<p>Nextdoor is a powerful channel for local mobilisation and awareness but unsuitable as a core participatory platform. It can be leveraged for community outreach but needs to be complemented by more structured engagement tools.</p>	

BRING THE FOOD	
<p>Purpose: Recovery and donation of surplus food</p> <p>Domain: Food waste prevention, circular economy</p> <p>Technical maturity: Functional, NGO-academic-backed tool with a clear mission</p>	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tailored to food redistribution and surplus management. - Strong social and environmental orientation. - Successfully deployed in operational food recovery networks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The narrow scope is limited to logistical coordination. - It does not support broader participatory engagement. - Dependent on active NGO or community partnerships.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highly relevant for LLs addressing local food waste and the redistribution of surplus. - It can be a backbone for food rescue initiatives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited scalability in contexts without strong civil society networks. - It may not support full participatory scope and co-creation.
<p>Bring the Food positively impacts food redistribution and complements participatory goals through practical application. It is best used with tools that foster community design or decision-making.</p>	

HOPLR	
Purpose: Neighbourhood engagement and community building	
Domain: Local social networking	
Technical maturity: Commercial platform with a growing European footprint	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encourages grassroots mobilisation and social cohesion. - Strong adoption in multiple EU cities. - Visually engaging and user-friendly interface. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited capacity for structured civic participation. - Closed-source with potential data sovereignty concerns. - No formal integration with policy or governance processes.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It can be used for mobilisation and informal dialogue. - Supports trust building in communities. - Hosts idea sharing, event coordination, or micro-projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overlap with other social media platforms (e.g. Facebook groups). - Risk of digital exclusion of non-digital users or those outside platform reach.
<p>HoplR is effective for local engagement and trust-building, especially at the early stages of citizen mobilisation. It can initiate participation but requires integration with more structured tools for co-design and decision-making.</p>	

OPEN FOOD NETWORK	
Purpose: Local food distribution, short supply chains	
Domain: Sustainable food system logistics	
Technical maturity: Open-source, deployed globally	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Built specifically for community-based food commerce. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires technical onboarding and administrative setup.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong open-source ethos and active support community. - Highly customisable and mission-aligned. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It may be too complex for small initiatives without support. - Focused more on logistics than engagement.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Anchor CSIs in real-world food distribution flows. - Facilitates consumer-producer connections aligned with sustainability goals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low uptake risk without capacity-building or facilitation. - Reliance on volunteer energy and local leadership can limit consistency.
<p>The Open Food Network's mission is to transform food systems from the ground up. When paired with engagement tools, it offers a real-world application layer for participatory innovation.</p>	

COMMONPLACE	
<p>Purpose: Urban planning consultation Domain: Public space and infrastructure engagement Technical maturity: Commercial, polished UI</p>	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visual, map-based public input collection. - Built-in sentiment and trend analysis tools. - Attractive and user-friendly interface. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developed for infrastructure and spatial planning. - Closed platform with proprietary architecture. - Limited scope for non-urban or food-related topics.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It can be repurposed for food infrastructure planning. - Useful for place-based co-design. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It competes with open-source mapping tools that offer similar functionality. - Adaptability constraints in low-tech or rural contexts.
<p>Commonplace is well-suited for spatial engagement and could support local food planning in urban areas. It should be seen as a complementary tool in environments that involve physical food infrastructure or land-use elements.</p>	

EPICOLLECTS
<p>Purpose: Mobile data collection Domain: Citizen science, field data</p>

Technical maturity: Open-source, university-supported	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mobile-friendly, multimedia-enabled data gathering. - Works offline and in remote settings. - Easy-to-use form builder with strong documentation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires training for consistent data quality. - Limited capacity for engagement beyond data collection. - It is not designed for deliberation or dialogue.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is ideal for participatory mapping, food access audits, or school-based activities. - Support data-driven storytelling and CS projects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement may be limited to the data collection phase. - Analysis and follow-up require additional platforms or skills.
<p>EpiCollect5 is a versatile and field-ready tool for participatory data collection. It strengthens citizen-generated evidence and bottom-up insights when embedded in broader engagement processes.</p>	

KIALO	
Purpose: Structured online debate and deliberation	
Domain: Public discourse, education, civic engagement	
Technical maturity: Commercial, globally deployed	
STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clear visual structure for complex arguments (pro/con tree format). - Encourages rational, evidence-based debate. - Supports anonymous and moderated participation. - Widely used in education and by civil society organisations. Works offline and in remote settings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not suited for spontaneous or emotional participation. - Requires digital literacy and time commitment. - Limited integration with other participatory tools.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is ideal for citizen consultations on polarising or complex issues. - Can support youth education, critical thinking, or pre-policy forums. - Scalable for multi-stakeholder deliberations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Confident or well-articulated voices may dominate debates. - Not optimised for data collection or participatory budgeting. - Risk of low participation if topics are not well scoped or facilitated.

Kialo is a structured online debate platform allowing users to map arguments for and against a central topic in a transparent, logical format. While it excels at clarifying complex or diverse issues, it requires careful facilitation to maintain inclusivity and engagement. Kialo is particularly useful for structured reflection, youth involvement, and pre-decision consultations in participatory food systems.

5 KEY FINDINGS AND GAPS IDENTIFIED

This chapter consolidates the main insights from the individual SWOT analyses, highlighting key strengths, recurring challenges, and shared opportunities across the assessed tools. It also outlines systemic risks and structural barriers that could hinder the adoption, scalability, or impact of digital tools within the SPOON project.

The findings offer strategic guidance for the further development, selection, and contextual adaptation of tools in CSLs and related participatory settings. They aim to support decision-making around toolset design, pilot implementation, and engagement planning, ensuring alignment with the project's inclusive, transparent, and sustainable food system transformation mission.

Table 2: Summary of key findings of digital tools

Tool	Purpose	Domain	Open Source	Technical Maturity	Participation Type	Adaptability	Integration Potential	Key Functions	Platform
Who's the Boss	Consumer awareness	Market transparency	No	Operational (Greece)	Voting & awareness	Low	Low	Consumer voting, campaign support	Web
CamBuildr	Visual campaigns	Digital marketing	No	Commercial, stable	Campaign design	Medium	Medium	Visual storytelling, campaign design	Web
Decidim	Participatory democracy	Civic tech	Yes	Highly mature	Deliberation & decision-making	High	High	Proposals, voting, assemblies	Web
Consul	Participatory budgeting	Public governance	Yes	Mature	Budgeting & co-decision	Medium-High	High	Budgeting, debates, structured input	Web

Polis	Opinion mapping	Public consultation	Partially	Cloud-based	Opinion clustering	Medium	Medium	Live opinion maps	Web
Synthetron	Stakeholder dialogue	Strategic consultation	No	Commercial, mature	Expert discussion	Low	Low	Moderated stakeholder dialogue	Web
Engagemen tHQ	Surveys and forums	Local engagement	No	Highly developed	Multi-modal input	Medium	Medium	Surveys, forums, mapping	Web
Go Vocal	Civic feedback	Local governance	No	Commercial	Quick feedback	Low	Low	Mobile surveys, feedback	Mobile
MindMixer	Idea generation	Public participation	No	Legacy, unclear	Idea crowdsourcing	Low	Low	Idea boards	Web
MetroQuest	Planning input	Urban planning	No	Commercial	Scenario feedback	Low	Low	Scenario-based input	Web
Nextdoor	Neighbourhood comms	Community networking	No	Very high	Local alerts & discussion	Medium	Medium	Neighbourhood news, discussions	Mobile & Web
Bring the Food	Surplus redistribution	Food waste	Partially	Functionally, NGO-backed	Surplus logistics	Medium	Medium	Food donation tracking	Mobile & Web
Hoplr	Neighbourhood engagement	Local networking	No	Commercial	Community ideas & mobilisation	Medium	Medium	Local events, volunteer calls	Mobile & Web
Open Food Network	Local food logistics	Food system logistics	Yes	Globally deployed	Marketplace & coordination	High	High	Online shops, logistics	Web
Commonplace	Planning consultation	Urban infrastructure	No	Commercial	Spatial feedback	Medium	Medium	Map-based comments	Web
EpiCollect5	Mobile data collection	Citizen science	Yes	University - supported	Data collection	High	High	Field data collection	Mobile

Kialo	Structured online debate	Public discourse, education	No	Commercial	Argument mapping, structured discourse	Medium	Low	Argument tree visualisation, multi-perspective debates	Web
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5.1 COMMON STRENGTHS ACROSS TOOLS

The assessment of selected tools reveals several recurring strengths that can inform the design and implementation of digital engagement strategies within the SPOON project.

A key strength across many platforms is user accessibility. Most tools feature intuitive user interfaces, mobile compatibility and low barriers to entry, making them suitable for engaging a wide spectrum of citizens regardless of digital literacy. Platforms like Go Vocal, Who's the Boss, and EngagementHQ excel in this regard, offering simple yet effective survey, voting, or feedback tools that support rapid deployment in the local context. Similarly, Hoplr and Nextdoor leverage familiar social networking principles to foster informal, peer-to-peer engagement at the neighbourhood level.

Another widely shared strength is the versatility of engagement formats. Many tools support multi-modal participation, combining surveys, idea boards, debates, mapping, and forums. This flexibility enables facilitators to tailor interaction strategies to local needs and to combine synchronous (like live dialogues in Synthetron or Polis) and asynchronous inputs (e.g. idea submissions in Decidim or MindMixer). Platforms like Decidim, Consul, and Commonplace are particularly valuable here due to their modular and extensible architectures.

Open-source availability is another major asset, especially in tools such as Decidim, Consul, Open Food Network, and EpiCollect5. These platforms support transparency and long-term cost-efficiency and align well with EU data sovereignty and digital ethics principles. Their active developer communities and continuous feature evolution increase their resilience and adaptability across varying contexts and governance models.

Furthermore, many tools show high technical maturity and real-world validation. Several have been successfully deployed by public authorities, research institutions, and grassroots organisations, demonstrating their practical utility and relevance. For example, Consul has been adopted by over 100 cities globally for participatory budgeting; Polis has been used in complex deliberations in national ministries; Bring the Food is embedded in functioning food redistribution networks; and Open Food Network is operating across multiple continents with strong community backing.

Lastly, several tools align clearly with sustainable food system transformation goals, even if not originally developed for this domain. Platforms such as Bring the Food and Open Food Network offer direct functionality for food redistribution and supply chain re-localisation. Though not food-specific, others foster collective agency and decision-making critical for food citizenship and community-based innovation.

5.2 SHARED LIMITATIONS AND WEAKNESSES

Despite their diverse strengths, the tools analysed also share several limitations that may constrain their effective deployment within the SPOON project and its CSLs.

One of the most prominent limitations is restricted adaptability across contexts. Many commercial or country-specific platforms, such as Who's the Boss, EngagementHQ, or MetroQuest, have been designed for specific policy environments, linguistic settings, or governance systems. As such, transferring them to new cultural or regulatory contexts often requires substantial localisation efforts in terms of content and functionality. Unless additional adaptation resources are available, their usefulness in transnational or multilingual initiatives like SPOON will be limited.

Another significant challenge is the technical or operational complexity of some of the more feature-rich or open-source tools. While platforms like Decidim, Consul, and Open Food Network offer powerful functionality and modular design, they typically require dedicated IT resources for initial setup, server hosting, user support, and ongoing maintenance. This can represent a major barrier to adoption and sustainability for smaller communities or project teams without in-house technical capacity. Similarly, tools like Synthetron depend heavily on professional facilitation and structured engagement design, which limits their applicability in informal, bottom-up or spontaneous community settings.

A further systemic limitation concerns several commercial tools' opacity and proprietary nature. Platforms like Go Vocal, EngagementHQ, and MindMixer, offer limited transparency regarding their data governance practices, long-term business models, and integration options. Their closed-source architecture concerns vendor lock-in, GDPR compliance, and alignment with EU principles of digital sovereignty and ethical data stewardship. This lack of openness also complicates efforts to adapt these tools for emerging needs or connect them with other components of the SPOON digital ecosystem.

Several tools also fail to enable deep co-creation or iterative collaboration. While many platforms effectively gather opinions, feedback, or votes (e.g., Polis, Nextdoor, CamBuildr), fewer offer robust support for sustained co-design, prototyping, or the structured incorporation of citizen-generated data into decision-making processes. This undermines their suitability for fostering long-term, participatory innovation, particularly when addressing complex challenges in sustainable food systems that require dialogue, experimentation, and learning across multiple cycles.

In addition to the major structural limitations discussed above, several recurring weaknesses emerged that may further constrain the effective use of digital tools in the SPOON project. One such concern is the risk of digital exclusion. Certain platforms, such as EpiCollect5 and MetroQuest, rely on stable internet access and a minimum level of digital literacy, which can inadvertently marginalise older adults, people living in remote or underserved areas, and individuals without access to smartphones or broadband infrastructure. These demographic groups are often among the most affected by food system challenges, making their exclusion from participatory processes particularly problematic.

A further limitation lies in the insufficient multilingual support provided by many platforms. Although some tools are used across different regions, they frequently lack full localisation into EU languages, hindering meaningful engagement from non-English-speaking participants. This gap limits inclusivity and may compromise the cultural relevance and accessibility of participatory processes in multilingual or linguistically diverse communities.

Another challenge is the short-term focus of several tools, especially those designed for specific campaigns or consultations. Platforms like CamBuildr and MindMixer, while effective for capturing opinions or feedback within a defined time window, often lack the features necessary to support long-term user engagement, community building, or iterative collaboration. This constrains their utility in projects like SPOON, which rely on sustained relationships and collective learning over time.

Finally, most tools do not include integrated mechanisms for monitoring or evaluating the outcomes of engagement activities. The absence of features to track the influence of citizen input on policies, behavioural change, or community dynamics limits the ability to assess the impact of participatory efforts. For SPOON, this presents a challenge in demonstrating the value of citizen science and co-creation processes, both internally and to external stakeholders.

These additional weaknesses underscore the importance of careful tool selection and contextual adaptation. They also highlight the need for complementary support measures, such as facilitation, translation, capacity-building, and monitoring frameworks, to ensure that digital engagement is accessible but also inclusive, meaningful, and impactful across diverse contexts.

5.3 EMERGING OPPORTUNITIES FOR SPOON

The comparative assessment of existing digital engagement tools reveals several strategic opportunities for the SPOON project to generate added value at the intersection of CS and sustainable food system transformation.

One of the most significant opportunities lies in bridging the persistent gap between engagement and concrete action. While many platforms effectively capture opinions, collect survey data, or visualise public sentiment, few offer integrated pathways that connect citizen input with structured decision-making, collaborative design, and tangible local interventions. SPOON is well-positioned to address this gap by developing tools beyond data collection, enabling evidence-informed co-creation, prototyping, and community-level implementation. This would enhance the relevance of citizen engagement by linking insights directly to food system outcomes and empowering communities to act on shared priorities.

A second opportunity emerges from the lack of food-system-specific digital functionalities. Although a few platforms, such as Bring the Food, touch on themes like food redistribution or waste reduction, none of the reviewed tools were originally conceived with the broader goals of sustainable nutrition, circular food economies, or behaviour change in mind. This opens up a clear innovation space for SPOON to embed food-relevant features into its engagement tools, such as food waste diaries, participatory meal planning, local sourcing challenges, community nutrition trackers, or behaviour nudging interfaces. These features would support health and sustainability agendas while creating a stronger connection between digital participation and everyday food practices.

There is also strong potential for SPOON to explore modular, hybrid engagement architectures, combining existing tools with bespoke components tailored to the specific needs of each CSL. For example, participatory mapping from Polis could be combined with the visual storytelling or campaign-building functions of CamBuildr to co-create community food narratives. Similarly, Consul's budgeting logic and transparency mechanisms could be adapted for local food micro-granting schemes, empowering residents to fund small-scale sustainability initiatives. Such hybrid approaches would allow SPOON to retain existing platforms' robustness and tested performance while introducing targeted innovations to respond to local priorities and contexts.

Lastly, the growing importance of data sovereignty, ethical participation, and digital democracy across Europe presents an opportunity for SPOON to differentiate itself from mainstream commercial engagement platforms. By grounding its toolset in open-source foundations such as Decidim or Consul, the project can promote citizen ownership of data, privacy-by-design, and transparent governance models. This would increase user trust and compliance with EU regulatory frameworks and foster long-term sustainability through community stewardship and interoperability with public-sector digital infrastructures.

Taken together, these opportunities suggest a clear direction for SPOON: to move beyond generic participation tools toward creating an engagement ecosystem that is domain-relevant, action-oriented, ethically grounded, and technically adaptable. Through smart integration, innovation, and user-centred design, SPOON can contribute meaningfully to shaping the next generation of participatory technologies for food system resilience and transformation.

5.4 SYSTEMIC RISK AND BARRIERS

Beyond the specific limitations of individual tools, the analysis highlights several systemic risks and structural barriers that could hinder the effective deployment, scaling, and long-term impact of citizen engagement solutions within the SPOON project and similar participatory initiatives.

One of the most persistent barriers is the digital divide, which limits inclusive participation across socio-demographic and geographic lines. Many tools rely on stable internet access, digital literacy, and access to personal digital devices, prerequisites that are not equally met across all user groups. As a result, there is a real risk of excluding those who are already most vulnerable to food insecurity, including older adults, rural residents, and individuals from lower socio-economic backgrounds. These gaps in access do not merely reflect technical limitations but point to deeper social inequalities that must be explicitly addressed in the design of participatory strategies.

A second systemic issue concerns the fragmentation and lack of interoperability between digital platforms. Most tools operate as standalone systems with limited capacity to interface with other platforms, datasets, or public digital infrastructures. Few provide open APIs or follow modular, standards-based design principles. This limits building cohesive, scalable toolchains across diverse LLs and user groups. Without deliberate efforts to ensure interoperability, projects risk duplicating effort, losing valuable citizen-generated data, and missing opportunities for cross-pilot learning and cumulative impact.

Institutional resistance and low political buy-in represent another critical barrier, particularly in governance settings where participatory processes are perceived as time-consuming, administratively burdensome, or politically sensitive. Tools that enable open deliberation, participatory budgeting, or public accountability, such as Decidim or Consul, require more than just technical deployment; they demand clear mandates, supportive leadership, and a culture of openness within public institutions. In contexts marked by fragmented authority, siloed decision-making, or weak public trust, such tools may face significant obstacles to adoption and impact.

Finally, rising concerns around privacy, trust, and ethical data use present a growing systemic risk in digital participation. Citizens are increasingly aware of how their data is collected, stored, and used, and any perception of surveillance, manipulation, or opacity can seriously undermine participation. Commercial platforms, in particular, often face credibility gaps unless equipped with robust safeguards, transparent governance models, and clear mechanisms for informed consent. For SPOON, this reinforces the need to adopt privacy-by-design principles, ensure full GDPR compliance, and build trust through participatory governance of digital tools, not as an afterthought but as a foundational component of its digital strategy.

Collectively, these systemic risks underscore the importance of taking a holistic, context-aware, and ethically grounded approach to deploying citizen engagement technologies. Proactively addressing these barriers will be essential for the success of individual tools and for SPOON's broader ambition to foster inclusive, legitimate, and impactful participation in the transition to sustainable food systems.

6 STRATEGIC DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT RECOMMENDATIONS FOR A CITIZEN SCIENCE TOOLSET

The following recommendations are based on the comparative SWOT analysis and synthesis of existing digital tools relevant to citizen science initiatives. They are intended to serve as a strategic design consideration, informed prioritisation, and inspiration for SPOON's tool development, which must reflect different CSL's and BCIs' needs. These suggestions highlight key functional, ethical and technical elements that could be explored over time, either within SPOON or through collaboration with complementary initiatives.

The overarching goal is to stimulate discussion and guide possible future directions in building a GDPR-compliant, inclusive, and user-friendly digital ecosystem that enables participatory food system innovation.

6.1 FUNCTIONAL GAPS TO ADDRESS

The analysis reveals several areas where existing tools do not fully meet the needs of community-driven engagement in food systems. These functional gaps could be considered as potential focus areas when shaping current and future tool design.

Most reviewed tools are general-purpose and lack domain-specific features tailored to sustainable food systems. A SPOON digital solution could explore integrating elements such as behaviour change prompts, circular food flow visualisations, or nutrition awareness modules, where technically and contextually feasible.

Additionally, while basic participation features (e.g. surveys, polls) are common, few platforms support end-to-end co-creation journeys. Supporting iterative citizen engagement, from issue identification to ideation and feedback, remains a longer-term ambition and may be approached through modular experimentation or partnerships.

Inclusivity also emerged as a concern. Many existing tools lack accessibility options or multilingual interfaces. Although not all gaps can be closed within SPOON's scope, adopting universal design principles and exploring low-barrier access options (e.g. SMS input, offline collection) could gradually improve equity and participation.

6.2 INTEROPERABILITY AND INTEGRATION STRATEGY

To ensure adaptability and long-term value, interoperability should be considered a guiding design principle. The use of open standards, modular data structures, and API-based

architecture can support future integration with CSL tools, public platforms, or other stakeholder systems.

Rather than creating a monolithic tool, SPOON could benefit from a component-based or hybrid model in which selected functionalities (e.g. surveys, visualisation) are added through external, well-documented tools where needed. For instance, embedding existing open-source solutions like Jotform or Consul, where applicable, could reduce development overhead while enhancing utility.

To encourage reuse beyond the project, SPOON could also document key integration practices, offer sample configurations, or host a lightweight knowledge-sharing hub for partners.

6.3 USER CENTRED DESIGN AND GDPR COMPLIANCE

Placing users at the centre of the design process remains a critical but scalable ambition. Within SPOON's timeframe, user testing and co-design efforts can be implemented in focused areas or only as feedback from CSL coordinators, interface feedback loops, community piloting, or low-fidelity prototyping, with a longer-term view of iterative improvement.

Equally important is SPOON's commitment to GDPR compliance and ethical data governance. Tools must ensure clear consent processes, transparent data use policies, and respect for user control. This is essential for building digital trust, especially in food-related contexts, where data may relate to health, lifestyle, or socio-economic status. The data governance framework will be built in the project.

While full institutional-grade governance structures may not be achievable during the project, transparency and accountability should be prioritised through clear documentation, simple terms of use, and visible community guidelines.

7 CONCLUSION

This report presents a comprehensive review of existing digital tools relevant to citizen participation and data exchange in the context of sustainable food systems. Through a structured SWOT analysis, the evaluation covers various platforms regarding their functionalities, usability, technical maturity, and alignment with SPOON's objectives.

The findings highlighted several common strengths, such as open-source availability, modular design, and validated engagement mechanisms, as well as critical weaknesses, including the lack of food-system-specific features, limited support for co-creation, and barriers to inclusivity and interoperability.

Based on this analysis, strategic recommendations have been formulated to guide the development of SPOON's digital toolset. These recommendations stress the importance of embedding domain-specific functionality, ensuring technical modularity and integration potential, and prioritising ethical, inclusive, and user-driven design. In doing so, SPOON can create tools that are effective and adaptable and contribute meaningfully to democratic innovation and food system transformation.

The outcomes of this work will directly inform the next phases of the SPOON project, particularly in activities which focus on the co-design and prototyping of SPOON's digital toolset. Moreover, the insights will support alignment with CSL's activities, stakeholder engagement strategies, and the development of digital infrastructures that are context-sensitive, participatory, and capable of driving impactful and inclusive food system innovation across Europe.

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9 ANNEXES

9.1 MATRIX FOR COLLECTING INITIAL INPUT

An Excel-based table was used for data collection, but the information is presented here in this format to ensure greater clarity and readability.

First Sheet: Instructions:

Thank you for completing this questionnaire. Please follow the instructions below to provide your input:

Go to the sheet *USE*.

Step 1: General Information

Enter the name of your organisation (select from partners). Indicate the name of the application you are providing information about and include a link to the application.

Step 2: Indicate Your Experience with the APP (Column D)

Please choose one of the following options:

- *Currently, use it.*
- *Plan to use it*
- *Never used it, but I like it*
- *Only heard about it*

Step 3: Navigate According to Your Answer

- If you selected *Currently, use it* → stay on the *USE* sheet.
- If you selected *plan to use it* →, go to the *plan to use* sheet (same row number).
- If you selected *Never used it, but like it*, → go to the *Like it* sheet (same row number).
- If you selected *Only heard about it*, → go to the *Heard* sheet (same row number).

Step 4: Complete the Relevant Sheet

Fill in all questions on the relevant sheet based on the selected option. Please provide as much detail as possible to help us better understand each application.

You may include information on multiple applications.

If you have any questions or need support, please contact us.

Thank you for your valuable input!

Second Sheet: Use

General Questions

Partner providing the info: Select your organisation from the list of project partners.

APP name: Name of the application.

Link: URL to the APP or its official page.

Usage: Indicate your current experience with the APP.

Adoption timeline: When you started or plan to start using the APP.

Ownership/Provider: Who owns or developed the APP, and whether it is open source or proprietary?

Functional and Usage Questions

Purpose: Main use of the APP (e.g., survey, citizen feedback, data reporting).

Target Audience: Intended users (e.g., general public, specific demographic groups).

Unique Strengths: Key advantages over similar tools.

APP Features: Core functions (e.g., survey creation, feedback collection).

Data Types Collected: Text, images, geolocation, videos, etc.

Real-Time Collection: Can it collect data live?

Customisation: Adaptability for specific needs.

Supported Devices/Platforms: Web, Android, iOS, etc.

User Interaction: How users interact (browser, app, SMS, phone).

Multi-Language Support: Is localisation available?

Ease of Use: Have any usability challenges been reported?

Scalability: Can it handle increased load?

Operational Questions

Integration: Compatibility with other tools (CRM, analytics, etc.).

Data Management: Storage methods, dashboard access.

Export Options: Availability and formats of data export.

User Feedback: Does it allow feedback or display results?

Acknowledgements: Auto replies or thank-you messages.

Response Rates: How are they tracked? Typical averages?

Effectiveness: Subjective evaluation of tool performance.

Privacy and Security Questions

Compliance: Does it meet data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR)?

Consent: How is informed consent ensured?

Data Anonymity: Can responses be anonymous? How is anonymity maintained?

Security: What measures are in place (e.g., encryption)?

Data Ownership: Who owns the collected data?

Adoption and Engagement Questions

Citizen Participation: How is uptake promoted?

Incentives: Are rewards used?

Accessibility: Is the tool inclusive for people with disabilities?

Interface Adjustments: For example, screen readers and simplified layout.

Feedback Mechanisms: Are users able to rate/report their experience?

User Resistance: Were there any adoption challenges?

Operational Costs and Resources

Cost: Licensing, subscriptions, etc.

Technical Support: Type and availability.

Resource Requirements: Staff infrastructure is needed.

Sustainability: Are long-term costs manageable?

Reflection and Challenges

Limitations: Known shortcomings.

Challenges: Implementation or usage problems.

Best Practices: Insights on effective use.

Expansion: Plans for broader use.

Vision: Future outlook (3–5 years).

Trends and Opportunities: Alignment with sector developments.

Improvement: Desired upgrades or features.

Risks/Threats: Competing tools or external changes.

Additional Information: Other relevant comments.

Contact Point: Who to reach out to for further details.

Third Sheet: Plan to use:**General Questions**

Partner providing the info: Select your organisation from the list of project partners.

APP name: State the name of the application.

Link: Provide a working URL to the application's main page or documentation.

Usage: Confirm that the APP is planned for future use.

Adoption timeline: Indicate when you plan to start using the APP.

Why: Explain why you chose this APP (e.g. affordability, specific features, recommendations).

Ownership/Provider: State who developed or owns the APP and whether it is open source or proprietary.

Functional and Usage Questions

Purpose: The main intended use of the APP (e.g., data collection, citizen feedback, reporting).

Target Audience: Who are the intended users (general public, specific groups)?

Unique Strengths: Identify specific advantages over similar tools.

Key Features: What functionalities are most relevant (e.g., surveys, reporting)?

Data Types Collected: Types of data you plan to gather (e.g., text, images, videos).

Customisation: Do you plan to configure or adapt the APP to your needs?

Supported Platforms: Which platforms will you use (web, iOS, Android)?

Ease of Use: Do you expect any usability issues?

Scalability: Can the APP handle increased users or data?

Operational Questions

Integration: Can the APP integrate with existing tools (e.g., CRMs, dashboards)?

Data Management: How will the data be stored and accessed?

Export Options: Are exports available? In which formats?

User Feedback: Will users receive results or feedback?

Acknowledgements: Can the APP send automated messages?

Response Metrics: Will you track engagement or response rates?

Effectiveness Evaluation: Have you assessed whether the APP meets your long-term goals?

Privacy and Security Questions

Compliance: Is the APP compliant with GDPR or similar frameworks?

Consent: How will informed consent be gathered?

Data Security & Anonymity: Do you have any concerns? What security measures are available (e.g., encryption)?

Data Ownership: Who owns the data collected through the APP?

Adoption and Engagement Questions

Accessibility: Could the tool present access challenges (e.g., disabilities, language)?

Feedback Mechanisms: Can users give feedback about their experience?

User Concerns: Have you identified risks of low adoption or engagement?

Operational Costs and Resources

Cost: What are the estimated costs (licensing, training, support)?

Resources: What internal resources (personnel, infrastructure) will be allocated?

Limitations: What are the known weaknesses or gaps in the tool?

Concerns: Are there uncertainties regarding the tool's performance?

Reflection and Future Outlook

Expansion: Do you plan to use the APP for other purposes later?

Vision: What is your 3–5 year outlook for the APP?

Success Factors: What could delay or hinder implementation?

Trends: Does the APP align with current digital trends or food system needs?

Improvement: Would you request specific upgrades from the provider?

Risks/Threats: Are there any competing tools or external risks?

Additional Information: Is there anything else worth noting?

Contact Point: Provide a contact person for follow-up.

Fourth Sheet: Like it:

General Questions

Partner providing the info: Select your organisation from the list.

APP name: State the name of the APP.

Link: Provide a URL to the APP or its main page.

Usage: Indicate your current experience (e.g. awareness, reviewed materials).

Why: Mention what aspects or features you find promising.

Ownership/Provider: Name the developer or owner. Specify if it's open source or proprietary.

Functional and Usage Questions

Purpose: What is the intended function (e.g., survey, reporting, engagement)?

Target Audience: Who would use this APP (general public, specific groups)?

Unique Strengths: What stands out compared to other tools?

APP Features: List functionalities you consider useful or innovative.

Other Opinions: Have you reviewed documents or discussed this APP with others?

Goals or Needs: How could this APP support your project goals (e.g., citizen science, outreach)?

Operational Questions

Integration: Could it be integrated with your current systems or tools?

Enhancement: How could it help improve existing workflows or address known challenges?

Privacy and Security Questions

Data Security: Have you reviewed how it handles data privacy?

Satisfaction: Is its approach satisfactory?

Regulatory Risks: Are there privacy or regulatory considerations to watch for?

Consent/Anonymity: Does the APP meet your consent and data handling standards?

Adoption and Engagement Questions

Target Users: Would the tool likely be accepted by your target group? Why?

Confidence Factors: What would boost your confidence in its effectiveness?

Operational Costs and Resources

Cost: Have you assessed potential adoption/maintenance costs?

Resource Needs: What support (staff, infrastructure) would be necessary for implementation?

Reflection and Challenges

Limitations: Are there any areas where the APP falls short?

Concerns: Are there uncertainties about its usability or fit?

Vision: What future role could this APP play in 3–5 years?

Trends: Does it align with relevant sector trends or digital innovations?

Risks: Are there competing tools that could reduce its relevance?

Threats: Are there external factors that could hinder adoption?

Additional Information: Is there anything else you'd like to share?

Contact Point: Provide a contact person for further communication.

Fifth Sheet: Heard about it

General Questions:

Partner providing the info: Select your organisation from the list of project partners.

APP name: Provide the name of the tool or application.

Link: If available, provide a URL to the APP's official page or documentation.

Usage: Confirm that you have only heard about this APP and have not used it.

Functional and Usage Questions

Purpose: What is the main goal of the APP (e.g., data reporting, feedback, awareness)?

Ownership/Provider: Who owns or developed the APP? Indicate whether it's open source or proprietary.

APP Features: What are the key features or functionalities based on what you know?

Feedback: Have you heard informal feedback about this APP (e.g., from other partners or networks)?

Other Users: Are you aware of any organisations or individuals using this APP?

Operational Questions

Data Security: Do you have any knowledge or assumptions about how the APP handles data privacy, consent, and protection?

Adoption and Engagement Questions

Target Audience: Who appears to be the intended audience for this APP?

Barriers: Are there any potential barriers to adoption that you foresee (e.g., cost, complexity, integration)?

Operational Costs and Resources

Cost: Do you have any information about pricing (e.g., licensing or subscription)?

Resource Requirements: Based on what you know, what kind of staffing or infrastructure might be needed for implementation?

Reflection and Challenges

Competition: Are there similar tools that might be more widely used or better suited?

Challenges: Are there concerns, uncertainties, or external risks related to this tool?

Additional Information: Any further comments, suggestions, or insights based on your APP awareness.

Contact Point: Provide your name or the name of someone who could be contacted for follow-up.

9.2 GLOSSARY AND SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Citizen Science (CS): The active involvement of non-professional scientists in generating, analysing, and disseminating data and knowledge.

Living Lab (LL): A real-life environment where users and stakeholders co-create and test new solutions in an open innovation ecosystem.

SWOT Analysis: A strategic planning method to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to a specific tool or strategy.

Interoperability: Different systems or platforms can exchange and use information seamlessly.

Open Source: Software whose source code is freely available for use, modification, and distribution.

Participatory Budgeting: A democratic process in which community members decide how to allocate part of a public budget.

GDPR: The General Data Protection Regulation is a legal framework that sets guidelines for collecting and processing personal data in the EU.

CONSORTIUM

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